

SOLUTION OF FRACTIONAL BURGERS EQUATION BY TWO INTEGRAL TRANSFORM BASED SEMI ANALYTICAL METHODS

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Abstract

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This study is concerned with the solution to a family of problems in mathematical physics referred to as Burgers equation. The fractional order Burgers equation considered is a nonlinear problem and can therefore not be solved by using any of the known analytical methods. Two hybrid methods are proposed for its solution; Shehu transform homotopy analysis method and Shehu transform Adomian decomposition method. The integral transform adopted, apart from generalizing the earlier transforms such as Laplace transform and Sumudu transform, it equally has the advantage of solving variable coefficients problems. After applying Shehu transform to every term in the given equation with the fractional order derivative interpreted in Caputo-Fabrizio sense, homotopy derivatives in homotopy analysis method and Adomian polynomials are respectively used to overcome the nonlinearities in the problem. Once that is accomplished, the inverse Shehu transform is taken to get the desired solution. These proposed methods are applied to solve some problems in literature, and the solutions those in the referenced literature. The results are tabulated and as well plotted in 3D graphs for ease of comparison. All the computations are carried out using Mathematica 13.0.

Keywords: Caputo-Fabrizio, Homotopy Derivative, Adomian Polynomial, Integral Transform

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Scientists have shifted their focus to the modelling of physical problems with the aid of non-integer order calculus. This is because interpretation based on the theory of non-integer derivatives gives perfect descriptions of physical phenomena. Fractional derivative is an extension of integer order, otherwise referred to as classical calculus. Its importance in the field of applied sciences cannot be overemphasized as it has distinct and broad applications in the fields of engineering such as viscoelasticity, electromagnetics, fluid mechanics, biological population models, signal processing, optics, just to mention a few (Frunzo, Garra, Guisti & Lungo, 2019; Gutierrez, Rosario & Machado, 2010; Machado, Kiryakova & Mainardi, 2011).

Numerous concepts of fractional derivatives can be found in literature. The widely accepted definitions are those given by Riemann-Liouville, Caputo and most recently Caputo-Fabrizio. But the first two suffer limitations in application due to their singular kernel. The latter, on the order

hand has wider application and better accuracy because its kernel is not singular (Anastacia, Emile, DOUNGMO & MELUSI; Caputo & Fabrizio, 2015; Ali, Saqib, Khan, & Sheikh, 2016). Certain processes associated with material multiplicity cannot be effectively described using the Riemann-Liouville or Caputo interpretations. That drawback was subsequently addressed by the definition developed by Caputo and Fabrizio which involves a kernel which is free of singularity $k(t, s) = e^{-\varphi(t-s)}$, $0 < \varphi < 1$.

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Burger’s equation named after Dutch mathematician Johnnes Martinus Burgers was invented in 1948, and it was observed to be a version of Navier-Stokes equation (Aminoordin & Puzi, 2024; Kumar, 2023). The said equation incorporates the Reynold number (Re) to model fluid flow, which measures the relative importance of viscous with inertia forces (Kumar, 2023). In 1915, Hary Bateman, an English mathematician, reported a new partial differential equation with the required initial conditions. Later in 1948, with the help of equation modelled by Bateman, Burgers was able to unravel the mathematical modelling of turbulence (Aminoordin & Puzi, 2024; Govind, 2012; Kumar, 2023). His rigorous work in fluid mechanics brought him to fame as one of the leading figures in that area. In addition, Everhard Hopf and Julian David Cole independently converted Burgers equation into linear heat equation that was solved for an arbitrary initial condition (Bonkile, Awashthi, Lakshmi, Mukundan & Aswin, 2018).

Shehu transform unifies both the Laplace and Sumudu transforms. It was introduced by Shehu Maitama and Weidong Zhao in 2019 (Yisa & Baruwa, 2022). It has been successfully applied to IVPs in ordinary and partial differential equations, integral and integro-differential equations. Researchers have used the transform to handle different nonlinear problems, especially when combined with semi-analytical methods, which the analytic method cannot solve (Adomian, 1994; Yisa, 2019; Yisa & Adelabu, 2022; Yisa & Tiamiyu, 2024). Additional advantages of Shehu transform over the well-known Laplace transform lie in its ability to solve variable coefficient problems.

In this research, we have proposed solutions to the Burgers equation using the well-known Shehu transform integrated with HAM and ADM. The essence of incorporating HAM is to exploit its derivative algorithm to overcome any nonlinear term that may be encountered. Adomian polynomials in ADM are to achieve the same purpose, as any nonlinear term is decomposed into a set of polynomials which is used recursively to get the desired solution.

1.1 Preliminaries

The Definition of Fractional Derivative by Caputo-Fabrizio (C-F)

The C-F derivative of order $\varphi \in (0,1)$ for a function $g(s)$ is defined as

$$\frac{M(\varphi)}{1-\varphi} \int_0^s g'(\tau) \exp\left(-\frac{\varphi}{1-\varphi}(s-\tau)\right) d\tau, \tag{1}$$

where

$M(\varphi)$ is a normalized function such that $M(0) = M(1) = 1$ often taken as $M(\varphi) = 1$,

$0 < \varphi < 1$ is the fractional order, and $g'(s)$ is the classical first derivative of $g(s)$.

Properties of Homotopy Derivative

The section presents a brief review of the HAM derivative and its properties.

Definition: Let σ be a function of the homotopy parameter γ , then

$$\beta_m(\sigma) = \frac{1}{\vartheta!} \frac{d^\vartheta \gamma}{d\gamma^\vartheta} \Big|_{\gamma=0} \tag{2}$$

is called the ϑ^{th} order homotopy derivative of σ , where $\vartheta \geq 0$ is an integer, and β_m is called the operator of ϑ^{th} order homotopy derivative.

The Zeroth and k^{th} Order Deformation Equations

There are basically two types of deformation equations in HAM and they are as given below.

The Zeroth order deformation equation is given as

$$(1 - \gamma)L[\phi(t; \gamma) - u_0(t)] = \gamma \mu N[\phi(t; \gamma)] \tag{3}$$

where $\gamma \in [0,1]$ is an embedding parameter, $\mu \neq 0$, L is an auxiliary linear operator, u_0 is an initial guess of $u(x)$, and $\phi(x; \gamma)$ is an unknown function.

While the k^{th} order deformation takes the form

$$[u_k(x) - \xi_{k-1}u_{k-1}(x)] = \mu \beta_{k-1} N[\phi(x; \gamma)], \tag{4}$$

where $\xi_k = \begin{cases} 0, & k \leq 1 \\ 1, & k > 1 \end{cases}$ and $\bar{\xi}_k = \begin{cases} 0, & k - 1 < 1 \\ 1, & k - 1 \geq 1 \end{cases}$

2.0 A Brief Review of Shehu Transform Method

2.1 Definition of Shehu Transform

The Shehu transform of a function $g(t)$ which is of the exponential order is defined as

$$\mathbb{S}\{g(t)\} = \int_0^\infty \exp\left(\frac{-s}{u}t\right)g(t)dt = G(s, u) \tag{5}$$

$$\mathbb{S}\{g(t)\} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^n \exp\left(\frac{-s}{u}t\right)g(t)dt, \quad s > 0, u > 0 \tag{6}$$

If the limit in (6) exists, it converges, otherwise it diverges.

The inverse Shehu transform is given as

$$\mathbb{S}^{-1}[G(s, u)] = g(t), \quad t \geq 0 \tag{7}$$

Definition of Shehu Transform Based on C-F

Consider the fractional derivative of order φ given as $D_t^\varphi f(t)$.

The Shehu transform of a fractional derivate of order φ for a function $g(t)$ is given as

$$\mathbb{S}\{ {}^{CF}_0 D_t^\varphi g(t) \} = \frac{sG(s, u) - ug(0)}{s + \varphi(u - s)}, \tag{8}$$

where CF means Caputo Fabrizioo.

Theorem: Let $g(x)$ be a smooth function defined on $[a, b]$, with the C-F derivative of $g(x)$ given as

$${}^{CF}_a D_x^\alpha g(x) = \frac{M(\alpha)}{1 - \alpha} \int_a^x e^{\alpha \frac{(x-t)}{1-\alpha}} g'(t) dt,$$

if $M(\alpha)$ is a normalized function and α is a fractional order derivative, then the Shehu transform of Caputo Fabrizioo is

$$\mathbb{S}\{ {}^{CF}_0 D_x^\alpha g(t) \} = \frac{sG(s, u) - ug(x)}{s + \alpha(u - s)}.$$

Proof: From the definition of normalized function, $M(\alpha), M(0) = M(1) = 1$.

$${}^{CF}_a D_x^\alpha g(x) = \frac{M(\alpha)}{1 - \alpha} \int_a^x e^{\alpha \frac{(x-t)}{1-\alpha}} g'(t) dt,$$

Taking the Shehu transform to both sides of (i), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{S}\{ {}^{CF}_0 D_x^\alpha g(t) \} &= \mathbb{S}\left\{ \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \int_0^x e^{\alpha \frac{(x-t)}{1-\alpha}} g'(t) dt \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \mathbb{S}\left\{ \int_0^x e^{\alpha \frac{(x-t)}{1-\alpha}} g'(t) dt \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Applying the convolution theorem to the integral, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{S}\{ {}^{CF}_0 D_x^\alpha g(t) \} &= \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \mathbb{S}\left\{ e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}t} * g'(t) \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{iv}$$

Which yields

$$\mathbb{S}\{ {}^{CF}_0 D_x^\alpha g(t) \} = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \mathbb{S}\left\{ e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}t} \right\} \mathbb{S}\{g'(t)\} \tag{v}$$

Since $\mathbb{S}\{e^{at}\} = \frac{u}{s-au}$,

$$\mathbb{S}\{ {}^{CF}_0 D_x^\alpha g(t) \} = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \left\{ \frac{u}{s - \frac{-\alpha}{1-\alpha}u} \right\} \left\{ \frac{s}{u} G(s, u) - g(0) \right\} \tag{vi}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{S}\{ {}^{CF}_0 D_x^\alpha g(t) \} &= \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \left\{ \frac{u(1-\alpha)}{s + \alpha(u-s)} \right\} \left\{ \frac{s}{u} G(s, u) - g(0) \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{vii}$$

$$\mathbb{S}\{ {}^{CF}_0 D_x^\alpha g(t) \} = \frac{u}{s + \alpha(u-s)} \left\{ \frac{sG(s, u) - ug(0)}{u} \right\} \tag{viii}$$

Thus,

$$\mathbb{S}\{ {}^{CF}_0 D_x^\alpha g(t) \} = \frac{sG(s, u) - ug(0)}{s + \alpha(u-s)}. \tag{ix}$$

2.2 A brief Review of Adomian Decomposition Method

Consider a general functional equation of the form

$$Py(x) + Qy(x) + R(y(x)) = g(x) \tag{9}$$

where P denotes the highest-order linear differential operator, Q represents the remaining linear terms, R is a nonlinear operator and $g(x)$ is a known function.

Applying P^{-1} , the inverse of P , and rearranging the terms gives

$$y = \theta(x) - L^{-1}[Qu] - L^{-1}[R(u)], \tag{10}$$

where $\theta(x)$ accounts for terms arising from initial or boundary conditions plus the terms from inhomogeneous source term.

The ADM assumes that the solution $y(x)$ can be expressed as a convergent infinite series

$$y(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} y_n(x) \tag{11}$$

and the nonlinear term $R(y)$ can be decomposed into

$$R(y) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} A_m \tag{12}$$

where A_m are the Adomian polynomials generated from y_0, y_1, \dots, y_m according to the formula

$$A_m = \frac{1}{m!} \frac{d^m}{d\lambda^m} N(\sum_{k=0}^m \lambda^k y_k) | \lambda = 0, \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots \tag{13}$$

Nature of the Problem

In this research, the family of problem considered is the Burgers equation

$$\mathcal{V}u_{xx} + D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + uu_x = \tag{14}$$

with $u(x, t) = 2 - 2 \tanh x, \mathcal{V} \geq 0$ and α is the Fractional order of the derivative.

Numerical Experiment

In this section, the two methods of solutions proposed in the preceding sections shall be applied to problem (14).

Solution to the problem via Shehu Transform Homotopy Analysis Method (STHAM).

Consider the Time Fractional Burgers Equation.

$$\mathcal{V}u_{xx} + D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + uu_x = \tag{15}$$

With $u(x, t) = 2 - 2 \tanh x, \mathcal{V} \geq 0$.

Taking the Shehu transform of both sides of (14) and interpreting the fractional derivative in Caputo-Fabrizio sense:

$$\mathbb{S}\{D_t^\alpha u(x, t)\} = \mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}$$

But

$$\mathbb{S}\{{}^{CF}_0 D_t^\alpha u(x, t)\} = \frac{su(x, (s, u)) - uu(0)}{s + \alpha(u - s)}$$

where CF means Caputo-Fabrizio

$$\frac{su(x, (s, u)) - uu(0)}{s + \alpha(u - s)} = \mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}$$

$$su(x, (s, u)) - uu(0) = s + \alpha(u - s) \mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}$$

$$su(x, (s, u)) = uu(0) + (s + \alpha(u - s)) \mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}$$

Divide through by s

$$U(x, (s, u)) = \frac{u}{s}u(0) + \frac{1}{s}(s + \alpha(u - s)) \mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}$$

$$U(x, (s, u)) = \frac{u}{s}u(0) + \left(1 + \alpha\left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)\right) \mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\} \tag{16}$$

Applying HAM

$$L[u] = u(x, (s, u)), \text{ and } N[u] = u(x, (s, u)) - \frac{u}{s}u(0) - \left(1 + \alpha\left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)\right) \mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}$$

Using the m th order deformation equation

$$L[U_m(x, (s, u)) - \chi_m U_{m-1}(x, (s, u))] = hD_{m-1}N[u] \tag{17}$$

$$\begin{aligned} L[U_m(x, (s, u)) - \chi_m U_{m-1}(x, (s, u))] &= hD_{m-1}[u(x, (s, u)) - \frac{u}{s}u(0) - (1 + \alpha\left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right))\mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} U_m(x, (s, u)) &= \chi_m U_{m-1}(x, (s, u)) + hD_{m-1}[u(x, (s, u)) - \frac{u}{s}u(0) - (1 + \alpha\left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right))\mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} U_m(x, (s, u)) &= \chi_m U_{m-1}(x, (s, u)) + h[U_{m-1}(x, (s, u)) - (1 - \bar{\chi}_{m-1})\left(\frac{u}{s}u(0)\right) - (1 + \alpha\left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right))\mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}] \end{aligned}$$

Using $h = -1$,

$$\begin{aligned} U_m(x, (s, u)) &= \chi_m U_{m-1}(x, (s, u)) - 1[U_{m-1}(x, (s, u)) - (1 - \bar{\chi}_{m-1})\left(\frac{u}{s}u(0)\right) - (1 + \alpha\left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right))\mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}] \end{aligned}$$

$$U_m(x, (s, u)) = \chi_m U_{m-1}(x, (s, u)) - U_{m-1}(x, (s, u)) + (1 - \bar{\chi}_{m-1}) \left(\frac{u}{s} u(0)\right) + (1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)) \mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}$$

$$U_m(x, (s, u)) = -(1 - \chi_m) U_{m-1}(x, (s, u)) + (1 - \bar{\chi}_{m-1}) \left(\frac{u}{s} u(0)\right) + (1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)) \mathbb{S}\{-uu_x + \mathcal{V}u_{xx}\}$$

Applying the property of homotopy derivative

$$U_m(x, (s, u)) = -(1 - \chi_m) U_{m-1}(x, (s, u)) + (1 - \bar{\chi}_{m-1}) \left(\frac{u}{s} u(0)\right) + \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)\right) \mathbb{S}\{-\sum_{i=0}^{m-1} u_{m-1-i}(u_i)_x + \mathcal{V} \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} (u_{m-1-i})_{xx}\}$$

But $\chi_m = \begin{cases} 0, & m \leq 1 \\ 1, & m > 1 \end{cases}$

Also,

$$\bar{\chi}_m = \begin{cases} 0, & m - 1 < 1 \\ 1, & m - 1 \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

At $m = 1$:

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = -(1 - \chi_1) U_0(x, (s, u)) + (1 - \bar{\chi}_0) \left(\frac{u}{s} u(0)\right) + \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)\right) \mathbb{S}\{-\sum_{i=0}^0 u_{1-1-i}(u_i)_x + \mathcal{V} \sum_{i=0}^0 (u_{1-1-i})_{xx}\}$$

Applying the properties given in (18) and (19)

$$\chi_1 = 0 \text{ and } \bar{\chi}_0 = 0$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = -U_0(x, (s, u)) + \left(\frac{u}{s} u(0)\right) + \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)\right) \mathbb{S}\{-u_0(u_0)_x + \mathcal{V}(u_0)_{xx}\}$$

To obtain u_0 the Taylor series is used which is given as

$$u(x, t) = u(a, b) + u_x(a, b)(x - a) + u_t(a, b)(t - b) + \frac{1}{2!} u_{xx}(a, b)(x - a)^2 + \frac{1}{2!} 2u_{xx}(a, b)(x - a)(t - b) + \frac{1}{2!} u_{tt}(a, b)(t - b)^2 + \dots, \tag{20}$$

Since

$$u(x, 0) = 2 - 2 \tanh x, \text{ then } u_x = -2 \operatorname{sech}^2 x, u_{xx} = 4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x, u_t = 0, u_{tt} = 0, u_{tx} = 0.$$

Substituting all the results in (20), we obtain

$$u_0 = 2 - 2 \tanh x, (u_0)_x = -2 \operatorname{sech}^2 x, (u_0)_{xx} = 4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = -u_0(x, (s, u)) + \left(\frac{u}{s} u(0)\right) + \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)\right) \mathbb{S}\{-2 \tanh x(-2 \operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V}(4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x)\} \tag{18}$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = -\frac{u}{s} (2 - 2 \tanh x) + \frac{u}{s} (2 - 2 \tanh x) + \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)\right) \mathbb{S}\{-2 \tanh x - 2 \operatorname{sech}^2 x + \mathcal{V}(4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x)\} \tag{19}$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)\right) \mathbb{S}\{(4 - 4 \tanh x)(\operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V}(4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x)\}$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)\right) \mathbb{S}\{1\} \{(4 - 4 \tanh x)(\operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V}(4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x)\}$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1\right)\right) \mathbb{S}\{1\} \{(4 - 4 \tanh x)(\operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V}(4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x)\}$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{u}{s} \right) \{ (4 - 4 \tanh x) (\operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V} (4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x) \} \right)$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = \left(\frac{u}{s} + \alpha \left(\frac{u^2}{s^2} - \frac{u}{s} \right) \{ (4 - 4 \tanh x) (\operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V} (4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x) \} \right)$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = \left(\frac{u}{s} + \alpha \left(\frac{u^2}{s^2} - \frac{u}{s} \right) \{ (4 - 4 \tanh x) (\operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V} (4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x) \} \right)$$

Taking the inverse Shehu transform of both sides

$$u_1(x, t) = (1 + \alpha (t - 1) (4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x) [1 - \tanh x + \mathcal{V} \tanh x])$$

Using $\mathcal{V} = 1$:

$$u_1(x, t) = (1 + \alpha (t - 1) (4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x)).$$

At $m = 2$:

$$u_2(x, t) = 4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x [(1 + \alpha (t - 1))^2 (8 - 4 \tanh x) + 1 (1 + \alpha (t - 1))]$$

The series solution is

$$u(x, t) = u_0 + u_1 + u_2 + \dots$$

$$u(x, t) = 2 - 2 \tanh x + (1 + \alpha (t - 1) (4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x) + 4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x) [(1 + \alpha (t - 1))^2 (8 - 4 \tanh x) + 1 (1 + \alpha (t - 1))] + \dots$$

Solution to the problem via Shehu Transform Adomian Decomposition Method (STADM)

Consider the Time Fractional Burgers Equation (15).

Applying ADM on equation (16)

$$U_{n+1}(x, (s, u)) = \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1 \right) \mathbb{S} \left\{ - \sum_{i=0}^n u_{n-i} (u_i)_x + \mathcal{V} \sum_{i=0}^n (u_i)_{xx} \right\} \right)$$

At $n = 0$:

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = (1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1 \right) \mathbb{S} \{ -u_0 (u_0)_x + \mathcal{V} (u_0)_{xx} \}) \tag{21}$$

To obtain u_0 the Taylor series is used which is given as

$$u(x, t) = u(a, b) + u_x(a, b)(x - a) + u_t(a, b)(t - b) + \frac{1}{2!} u_{xx}(a, b)(x - a)^2 + \frac{1}{2!} 2u_{xt}(a, b)(x - a)(t - b) + \frac{1}{2!} u_{tt}(a, b)(t - b)^2 + \dots \tag{22}$$

Since

$$u(x, 0) = 2 - 2 \tanh x, \text{ then } u_x = -2 \operatorname{sech}^2 x, u_{xx} = 4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x, u_t = 0, u_{tt} = 0, u_{tx} = 0,$$

Substituting all the results of (22) in (21), we obtain

$$u_0 = 2 - 2 \tanh x, (u_0)_x = -2 \operatorname{sech}^2 x, (u_0)_{xx} = 4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1 \right) \mathbb{S} \{ -(2 - 2 \tanh x) (-2 \operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V} (4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x) \} \right)$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1 \right) \mathbb{S} \{ (4 - 4 \tanh x) (\operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V} (4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x) \} \right)$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1 \right) \right) \mathbb{S}\{1\} \{ (4 - 4 \tanh x) (\operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V}(4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x) \}$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{u}{s} - 1 \right) \right) \left(\frac{u}{s} \right) \{ (4 - 4 \tanh x) (\operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V}(4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x) \}$$

$$U_1(x, (s, u)) = \left(\frac{u}{s} + \alpha \left(\frac{u^2}{s^2} - \frac{u}{s} \right) \right) \{ (4 - 4 \tanh x) (\operatorname{sech}^2 x) + \mathcal{V}(4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x) \}$$

Taking the inverse Shehu transform

$$u_1(x, t) = (1 + \alpha (t - 1)) (4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x) [1 - \tanh x + \mathcal{V} \tanh x]$$

At $\mathcal{V} = 1$:

Table 1: Exact and Approximate Solution by STHAM and STADM for $\alpha = 0.25$

t	STHAM $u(x, t)$	STADM $u(x, t)$	Exact $u(x, t)$
0.1	0.604	0.598	0.603
0.2	0.576	0.570	0.575
0.3	0.559	0.553	0.558
0.4	0.547	0.541	0.545
0.5	0.538	0.531	0.536
0.6	0.531	0.524	0.528
0.7	0.524	0.517	0.521
0.8	0.519	0.511	0.515
0.9	0.514	0.507	0.510
1.0	0.509	0.502	0.505

Table 2: Exact and Approximate Solution by STHAM and STADM for $\alpha = 0.5$

t	STHAM $u(x, t)$	STADM $u(x, t)$	Exact $u(x, t)$
0.1	0.678	0.673	0.677
0.2	0.627	0.621	0.625
0.3	0.593	0.587	0.592

$$u_1(x, t) = (1 + \alpha (t - 1)) (4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x) [1 - \tanh x + \tanh x]$$

When $n = 1$:

$$u_2(x, t) = 4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x [(1 + \alpha (t - 1))^2 (8 - 4 \tanh x) + (1 + \alpha (t - 1))]$$

The series solution is

$$u(x, t) = u_0 + u_1 + u_2 + \dots$$

$$u(x, t) = 2 - 2 \tanh x + (1 + \alpha (t - 1)) (4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x) + 4 \operatorname{sech}^2 x \tanh x [(1 + \alpha (t - 1))^2 (8 - 4 \tanh x) + 1(1 + \alpha (t - 1))] + \dots$$

Tabular Presentation of Results

The results obtained for Burgers equation in (15) through the two hybrid methods STHAM and STADM evaluated at various values of t and specific value of α are presented in the tables of values below.

0.4	0.568	0.562	0.566
0.5	0.549	0.542	0.546
0.6	0.532	0.525	0.529
0.7	0.518	0.511	0.515
0.8	0.506	0.499	0.502
0.9	0.495	0.488	0.491
1.0	0.485	0.478	0.481

Table 3: Exact and Approximate Solution by STHAM and STADM for $\alpha = 0.75$

t	STHAM $u(x, t)$	STADM $u(x, t)$	Exact $u(x, t)$
0.1	0.750	0.745	0.750
0.2	0.688	0.682	0.686
0.3	0.639	0.633	0.637
0.4	0.600	0.593	0.598
0.5	0.568	0.561	0.565
0.6	0.541	0.534	0.538
0.7	0.518	0.510	0.514
0.8	0.497	0.490	0.493
0.9	0.479	0.472	0.474
1.0	0.462	0.455	0.457

3D Graphs of $u(x, t)$ Against x and t for various values of α

Figure 1: The Graph of STHAM and STADM of $u(x, t)$ Against x and t for $\alpha = 0.25$

Figure 2: The Graph of STHAM and STADM of $u(x, t)$ Against x and t for $\alpha = 0.50$

Figure 3: The Graph of STHAM and STADM of $u(x, t)$ Against x and t for $\alpha = 0.75$

3.0 Results and Discussions

The results obtained for fractional order Burgers equation using STHAM and STADM with the fractional order interpreted in Caputo-Fabrizio sense are present in Tables 1, 2 and 3 together with the corresponding exact solutions. To validate the results obtained through our method, results obtained using these two hybrid methods are compared with results in existing literature. Precisely, (Saad & Al-Sharif, 2017) applied variational iteration method (VIM) to solve time fractional Burgers equation and his results though not tabulated but 3D graphs the authors presented are exactly like ours. Figure 1 presents the approximate solution for Problem 1 at $\alpha = 0.25$ and $\mathcal{V} = 1$. The 3D graph is similar to that obtained by (Saad & Al-Sharif, 2017) at $\alpha = 0.25$ and $\mathcal{V} = 1$. Also, 3D representation of the exact solution for $\alpha = 0.5$ and $\mathcal{V} = 1$ as shown in (Guo-Cheng Wu, 2016) bears a very close resemblance to that of Figure 2 which is the 3D graph at $\alpha = 0.5$ and $\mathcal{V} = 1$. The same explanation hold for 3D graph for Table 3 which is in agreement with the result in the existing literature (Guo-Cheng Wu, 2016; Saad & Al-Sharif, 2017). Although the cited literature did not put the result in tabular form, we believe that presenting the numerical values for the result will ease the task of comparison.

4.0 Conclusion

In conclusion, the STHAM and STADM have been successfully applied to solve the time fractional Burgers equation with the fractional derivative interpreted in Caputo-Fabrizio sense. The Caputo-Fabrizio is selected because it uses the non-singular exponential kernel whereas the classical Caputo derivative has singularity in the kernel. The results obtained are in close agreement with the exact solutions, and with those in existing literature where

different methods of solution were adopted. The computations were carried out using Mathematica 13.3.

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